

Overstimulation vs. Understimulation: A Search Trend Analysis

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Topic: Overstimulation vs. Understimulation

Title: Overstimulation vs. Understimulation: A Search Trend Analysis

Objectives: To compare American search interest in overstimulation and understimulation in health contexts over the past 5 years

Background: Overstimulation happens when the brain receives more input than it can efficiently process, often leading to stress and anxiety. It's commonly discussed in relation to screen time, especially in children. On the other hand, understimulation- a lack of sensory or mental engagement- gets far less attention, even though it also affects mental health. This study uses Google Trends to compare search interest in overstimulation to understimulation, and to highlight the need for more awareness of both.

Methods: To compare search popularity, I generated an *interest over time* chart by inputting the following search terms into the Google Trends Analysis search bar: *overstimulation*, and *low stimulation*. Thereafter, I specified the search category to *Health* to maintain focus and set the time range to generate data from the past 5 years. I then downloaded the *interest over time* chart and exported it to Microsoft Excel for analysis.

Results: From July 2020 to July 2025, the mean value of relative American search interest in *overstimulation* was 57.7% of the maximum interest in the dataset (SD = 16.7). In contrast, *low stimulation* had a mean interest of 15.3% (SD = 13.1).

Conclusions: Public interest in overstimulation far exceeds that of understimulation. Scientists could increase awareness of both these extremes of stimulation, especially to guide parents and guardians toward better understanding sensory-related behaviors in children.

Keyword 1: Overstimulation

Keyword 2: Low Stimulation

Keyword 3: Understimulation

Keyword 4: Cocomelon

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